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Research Article

Antimicrobial Resistance Profiling and Virulence Factors of Gram-Negative Bacteria Recovered from Poultry

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ABSTRACT

Poultry farming is a significant sector of the global agriculture industry that has been identified as a major reservoir for pathogenic organisms. The widespread and indiscriminate utilization of antibiotics in poultry production, for both therapeutic and growth-encouraging purposes, has contributed to the emergence and spread of antibiotic-resistant strains. Poultry litter harbors antimicrobial remnants and antibiotic-resistant bacteria, when used as fertilizer brings potential environmental risks posed by pharmaceutical residues and antimicrobial-resistant bacteria. The focus of this investigation was to determine the susceptibility patterns of poultry isolates to different antibiotic classes. Sum of 19 Gram negative bacterial isolates were detected from poultry litter and feed samples. The isolates were classified into three different bacterial genera namely *Escherichia* spp., *Proteus* spp., and *Pseudomonas* spp.. The isolates showed a moderate degree of resistance to nitrofurantoin, doxycycline hydrochloride, amoxiclav, and ampicillin, where 35.7% were resistant to ampicillin, 28.5% to cefotaxime and 7.14% to chloramphenicol. Variation in virulence factors expression among the isolates and their association with multidrug resistance (MDR) were also included in the study. The occurrence of moderate-level of resistance in poultry strains is an alarming situation poses great economic and major public health concern. These observations point to poultry farms as potential reservoirs of bacteria resistant to antibiotics that pose a risk of transmission to humans via the food chain. Hence, evaluating and ensuring the utilization of antibiotics in synergistic combinations is crucial to achieve effective outcomes and minimize the risk of emerging resistance development.

INTRODUCTION

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Poultry industry is a highly profitable source of high-quality protein that is consumed by people all over the world^[1]. Poultry included any human-domesticated birds like turkey, pigeons, duck, quail, chicken etc. With increasing population and escalating protein consumption, the poultry sector is set to experience continued growth in the near future, significantly contributing towards country's food security, economic growth and providing employment opportunities as well. This industry has well-built expansion from metropolitan cities to rural areas^[2]. Among livestock management methods, poultry production stands out for its efficiency in natural resource utilization and protein yield, it can significantly impact the human health and the environment^[3]. Waste products, including manure and poultry litter, are frequently produced in greater quantities and are required to fertilize the agricultural land. This may result in overuse and pose a significant risk to both water and soil quality. To prevent environmental pollution and safeguard human health, the by-product waste requires careful handling and control^[4]. In addition, poultry manure may carry microbes and pharmaceutical residues, including antibiotics used in poultry farming, which can lead to soil and water contamination and contribute to antimicrobial resistance in nearby ecosystems. A key requirement for the optimal growth (irreversible increase in body size and weight) of poultry is the supply of quality and nutritious feed supplements. These feeds come in various types, such as, growers, chick, starters, finisher mash, and layers containing varying constituents like cereals, vegetable protein, antioxidants, essential amino acids, animal protein, salt, antibiotics, vitamin premixes, and minerals. The specific composition depends on the desired outcomes set by the poultry farmer. In poultry production, antibiotics are extensively used both as growth promoters and to manage infectious diseases,

thereby improving growth performance and poultry quality^[5]. Poultry litter, when used as fertilizer, carries the risk of spreading pharmaceutical residues and antibiotic-resistant bacteria, the presence and impact of these in the environment are highly concerning^[6]. The widespread and unregulated use of antibiotics has led many bacteria to develop multidrug resistance (MDR). Growing antimicrobial resistance has emerged as a critical challenge to sustainable economic advancement^[7]. The excessive and inappropriate use of antibiotics in both human medicine and agriculture poultry contributes greatly to the emergence and dissemination of antibiotic resistant bacteria, posing a risk of transmission to humans via food or direct interaction with infected livestock^[8]. Antimicrobial resistance stands out as a major public health threat and continues to be a central topic for both researchers and healthcare professionals. Healthcare workers are currently facing a significant difficulty due to the increase in antibiotic resistance in gram-negative bacteria^[9]. Managing infections with multi-drug-resistant organisms (MDROs) involves significant therapeutic obstacles. The antibiotic pipeline is shrinking, and no novel antimicrobial treatments are projected soon for MDRO infections^[10]. The reason behind the accelerated emergence of bacterial resistance is the misuse of antibiotics in the treatment of infections^[7]. Antibiotics are vital for human infection treatment and prevention, but they are also widely administered in livestock, potentially serving as sources of antibiotic-resistant bacteria and antimicrobial resistance determinants transmissible to humans^[11]. Globally, antimicrobial resistance is acknowledged as a top threat to public health, complicating the treatment of infections and leading to elevated morbidity and mortality rates. The presence of multidrug resistant (MDR) bacteria may adversely affect the poultry industry

and thereby may affect the nation food production and safety which can have a financial impact on farmers and the food supply chain. The current study has been designed to address the multifaceted challenges posed by antimicrobial resistance in poultry production, contributing to public health safety, economic stability, and environmental sustainability by providing insights into the prevalence and resistance patterns of bacteria in poultry, and guiding better practices in antibiotic use and waste management. Further association between multidrug resistant isolates and their virulence factors has also been studied. Gaining insight into the extent of antibiotic resistance in poultry lays the groundwork for creating a surveillance system and supports the assessment of strategies aimed at limiting its spread. Monitoring and surveillance of antibiotic resistance at poultry farms can help to mitigate the direct or indirect transmission of resistant bacteria from poultry to humans via environmental pathways. The multidrug resistance producing bacteria from poultry industry are still missing from this region of the country. Therefore, the present study has been designed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sample collection site

In total eight poultry samples including poultry litter and poultry feed were aseptically collected from a regional Poultry Farm at Shimla, Himachal Pradesh. Rhode Island Red (RIR) was the only chicken breed rearing in the poultry farm. The sampling was done regularly from the same site at two-week intervals (weeks 0, 2, 4, and 6). Samples were transported same day to the research laboratory at Department of Microbiology, Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla for continued investigations.

Bacterial isolation and identification

One gram of each sample is suspended with 10ml of sterile normal saline to form original stock solution and further diluted upto 10^{-9} following 10-fold serial dilutions. An inoculum of 0.1 ml of each sample from the dilutions 10^{-5} and 10^{-6} were inoculated onto nutrient agar plate using spread plate technique. The plates were incubated aerobically at 37°C for 18-24 hours. Colony characteristics including color, size, shape, elevation, and overall appearance were examined. Pure colonies were observed on nutrient agar plates using streak plate method and further differentiation between lactose and non-lactose fermenters was done using MacConkey agar. Morphological features were assessed through microscopic examination of gram-stained preparations, and standard biochemical tests were conducted for further microbial identification. The biochemical profiles of each organism were interpreted according to the guidelines outlined in Bergey's Manual of Determinative Bacteriology. Purified culture isolates were preserved in 10% (v/v) glycerol stocks at -20°C for future investigations.

In vitro cultural sensitivity assay

Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of bacterial isolates was assessed following standard Kirby Bauer disc diffusion method. Inoculums were prepared by emulsifying the bacterial cultures in normal saline and the turbidity was compared using 0.5 McFarland standard which is equivalent to 1.5×10^8 CFU/ml. Commercially available antibiotics (Dodeca G-XI-minus DE045) were used namely ; Amikacin (30 mcg), Amoxy-Clavulanic acid (30 mcg), Ampicillin (10mcg), Cefepime (30mcg), Cefotaxime (30mcg), Ceftriaxone (30mcg), Chloramphenicol (30mcg), Doxycycline HCl (30mcg), Gentamicin (10mcg), Nitrofurantoin (300mcg), Norfloxacin (10mcg) and Tobramycin (10mcg). The antibiotic rings

were aseptically placed onto the inoculated Muller-Hinton agar plates with the help of sterile forceps. The plates were aerobically incubated at 37°C for 18-24 hours. The inhibition zones were recorded after 24 hours of incubation and interpreted as sensitive, intermediate and resistant as per the reference standard provided with the antibiotic discs^[12].

Determination of virulence attributes

Bacterial isolates were further examined for the presence of selected virulence factors which includes lipase and protease production, motility, siderophore and biofilm formation following standard procedures^[13].

RESULTS

Table 1: Source distribution of identified bacterial genera from poultry

Sample Source	Bacterial Genera		
	<i>Proteus Spp.</i>	<i>Escherichia Spp.</i>	<i>Pseudomonas Spp.</i>
Poultry Litter	10	3	0
Poultry Feed	4	0	2

Antibiotic susceptibility pattern of bacterial isolates

Bacterial isolates recovered from poultry litter and feed exhibited variable antibiotic susceptibility pattern. Maximum resistance was observed for Amoxy-Clavulanic acid and Doxycycline hydrochloride (46.37%) followed by Nitrofurantoin (42.10%), Ampicillin (31.58%) while it was lower for Chloramphenicol, Cefepime and Cefotaxime. In contrast, bacterial isolates were found susceptible to Amikacin, Ceftriaxone,

Bacterial Identification

The presence of clinically significant bacterial species was investigated in poultry litter and feed samples. Total 21 bacterial isolates were recovered from which 19 were identified as gram-negative bacteria and 2 were gram-positive bacteria. Only gram-negative bacteria were incorporated in this study. 13 gram-negative bacterial isolates were recovered from poultry litter while 6 isolates had their source from poultry feed. All the gram-negative isolates belonged to 3 different bacterial genera, namely *Escherichia spp.* (3 isolates), *Proteus spp.* (14 isolates) and *Pseudomonas spp.* (2 isolates) and their source wise distribution are presented in Table 1.

Norfloxacin, Tobramycin and Gentamicin. Multidrug resistant (MDR) phenotype was more common in poultry litter (5/13) than poultry feed samples (1/6). Higher incidence (30.76%) of MDR phenotypes was observed among *Proteus spp.* recovered from poultry litter while it was 7.69% for *Escherichia spp.* The only isolate from poultry feed showing drug resistant phenotype was *Proteus spp.* The antibiogram showing antibiotic susceptibility pattern and resistant phenotype among isolates is summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Antibiogram of bacterial isolates (n=19) showing resistance (Red) and sensitive (Yellow) and distribution of MDR & MDS isolates among sample source.

Genus	Source	AK	AMC	CTR	CTX	CPM	DO	NX	TOB	GEN	AMP	NIT	C	Total Sensitive (%)	Total Resistant (%)	Resistant phenotype
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Yellow	66.666 66667	33.333 33333	MDR
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Red	Yellow	91.666 66667	8.3333 33333	MDS									
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	58.333 33333	41.666 66667	MDR
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Yellow	66.666 66667	33.333 33333	MDR
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	83.333 33333	16.666 66667	MDS
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Yellow	75	25	MDR
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Red	Yellow	91.666 66667	8.3333 33333	MDS									
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	100	0	MDS											
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	100	0	MDS											
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P L	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	83.333 33333	16.666 66667	MDS
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P F	Yellow	100	0	MDS											
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P F	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	75	25	MDR
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P F	Yellow	100	0	MDS											
<i>Proteus spp.</i>	P F	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	83.333 33333	16.666 66667	MDS

<i>Escherichia spp.</i>	P L												83.333 33333	16.666 66667	M D S
<i>Escherichia spp.</i>	P L												91.666 66667	8.3333 33333	M D S
<i>Escherichia spp.</i>	P L												66.666 66667	33.333 33333	M D R
<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>	P F												100	0	M D S
<i>Pseudomonas spp.</i>	P F												83.333 33333	16.666 66667	M D S
Total Sensitive (%)		1 0 0	52.6 3158	1 0 0	94.7 3684	94.7 3684	52.6 3158	1 0 0	1 0 0	1 0 0	68.4 2105	57.8 9474	89.4 7368		
Total Resistant (%)		0	47.3 6842	0	5.26 3158	5.26 3158	47.3 6842	0	0	0	31.5 7895	42.1 0526	10.5 2632		

Abbreviations: AK - Amikacin, AMC - Amoxycyclav, CTR - Ceftriaxone, CTX - Cefotaxime, CPM - Cefepime, DO - Doxycycline hydrochloride, NX - Norfloxacin, TOB - Tobramycin, GEN - Gentamicin, AMP - Ampicillin, NIT - Nitrofurantoin, C – Chloramphenicol, PL – Poultry Litter, PF – Poultry Feed, MDR – multidrug resistant, MDS – multidrug sensitive.

Table 3: Expression of virulence factors among Multidrug resistant (MDR) and Multidrug sensitive (MDS) bacterial phenotypes.

Bacterial Phenotype	Sample Source	<i>Proteus Spp.</i>	<i>Escherichia Spp.</i>	<i>Pseudomonas Spp.</i>	Lipase	Protease	Siderophore	Biofilm	Motility
MDR	Litter	4	1	0	5	5	5	5	
	FEED	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	
MDS	Litter	6	2	0	4	1	5	7	
	FEED	3	0	2	4	3	3	4	

Determination of virulence attributes

Poultry isolates were further evaluated for the presence of selected virulence traits using phenotypic tests. Overall 89.74% isolates were biofilm producers and 78.94% were found motile.

Lipase and siderophore production was observed among 73.68% isolates. The expression of protease as a virulence factor was observed for 52.63% isolates. A total of 6 MDR (multidrug resistant) and 13 MDS (multidrug sensitive) phenotypes were observed in the present study. All

studied virulence factors were equally expressed among MDR isolates from both the sources. However, a notable difference was identified in protease production among MDS isolates from poultry litter and feed samples (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to evaluate the emergence of MDR isolates among bacteria recovered from poultry. A tremendous increase in the accumulation of resistance determinants in clinically important bacteria is a worldwide problem. In the present study, 19 Gram negative bacterial isolates were isolated and identified. Out of these, 13 were from poultry litter and 6 were from poultry feed samples. The most predominant isolate was *Proteus spp.*, followed by *Escherichia spp.*, and *Pseudomonas spp.* The isolates expressed a moderate degree of resistance to nitrofurantoin, doxycycline hydrochloride, amoxycylav, and ampicillin in the present study. However, a low resistance to cefotaxime, cefepime, and chloramphenicol was observed. A total of 57.1% isolates of *Proteus spp.* showed resistance to doxycycline hydrochloride and nitrofurantoin, 35.7% were resistant to amoxycylav, 28.5% were resistant to ampicillin, 14.2% were resistant to cefotaxime, and 7.14% were resistant to cefepime and chloramphenicol. However, 100% isolates of *Escherichia spp.* were resistant to amoxycylav and 66.6% of isolates were resistant to ampicillin followed by 33.3% who were resistant to nitrofurantoin and doxycycline hydrochloride each. 50% isolates of *Pseudomonas spp.* were resistant to amoxycylav and chloramphenicol each. Most of the isolates were sensitive to other antibiotics (gentamycin, tobramycin, ceftriaxone, norfloxacin, and amikacin) used in the study. A study executed by Ezekiel *et al.*, 2011^[14] observed the high resistance among *E. coli* isolates recovered from poultry feed samples against

nitrofurantoin (100%) and amoxicillin (93.3%). Eyasu *et al.*, 2017^[15] observed high level of antimicrobial resistance among *E. coli* poultry isolates towards ampicillin (94.2%), followed by penicillin (92%), tetracycline (73%), erythromycin (66%) and the lowest resistance was recorded for kanamycin (2%). A study carried out by Shrestha *et al.*, 2017^[16] reported that the *E. coli* isolates were resistant to ampicillin whereas the isolates were sensitive to doxycycline hydrochloride and gentamicin. Sebastian *et al.*, 2021^[17] reported that the *E. coli* isolates were resistant to ampicillin, amoxicillin, amikacin and cefotaxime in their study. In our study, the rate of resistance among *Escherichia spp.* against amoxicillin (100%) and ampicillin (66.6%) was higher than in the study reported by Bushen *et al.*, 2021^[18]. In their study, *E. coli* demonstrated a 91.7% resistance rate against ampicillin, 66.7% against amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, and 54.2% against chloramphenicol. *P. mirabilis* isolates also exhibited resistance to ampicillin, amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, and chloramphenicol in their study which was higher as compared to our study. Overall 31.5% of isolates were identified as multiple drug-resistant bacteria in this study. Out of 6 MDR isolates, 1 (33.3%) was of *Escherichia spp.*, and 5 (35.7%) isolates belonged to *Proteus spp.* A study conducted by Ibrahim *et al.*, 2021^[19] reported a high level, i.e., 90% of the multidrug resistant isolates from poultry litter. However, Okonko *et al.*, 2010^[20] reported a moderate percentage of MDR isolates among *E. coli* (27.3%), and *Proteus mirabilis* (45.5%) isolates recovered from poultry feed. In the present study, almost 50% of *Proteus spp.* from poultry litter were reported as MDR resembling the findings of the study conducted by Bushen *et al.*, 2021^[18] who observed 50% of *P. mirabilis* poultry isolates as MDR. Despite high concentrations of incorporated antibiotics, multidrug-resistant organisms are still frequently observed. This points to the possibility

that low-potency antibiotics used during feed production have compromised their intended effectiveness. Consequently, evaluating and adopting synergistic antibiotic combinations are necessary to enhance effectiveness and minimize the risk of emergence of resistance. This might challenge the effectiveness of modern antimicrobial agents. The presence of clinically important virulence factors such as lipase, protease, siderophore production, biofilm formation, and motility among Multidrug resistant (MDR) & Multidrug sensitive (MDS) bacterial phenotypes has also been conducted in the present study. The occurrence of virulence factors among poultry isolates might result in increased morbidity and mortality rate in poultry farms. A total of 73.6% isolates were lipase and siderophore producers, and 52.6% of isolates were protease producers. *Proteus spp.* is the most significant producer of lipase, protease and siderophore especially among the isolates recovered from the poultry litter, while *Pseudomonas spp.* and *Escherichia spp.* showed minimal to no production. A total of 79% were found to be motile in our study which comprise of *Proteus* species (n=10), *Escherichia* (n=03) and *Pseudomonas* species (n=02). Channa *et al.*, 2019^[21] observed that all the *E. coli* isolates from poultry litter were non motile in their study. The similar results as our study were reported by Danbappa *et al.*, 2018^[22]. They observed that all poultry strains of *E. coli* and *Proteus spp.* were motile. In our study, 10.5% isolates were non biofilm producers, 36.8% were moderate producers, 42.1% were weak producers, and 10.5% were strong biofilm producers. Similar study carried out by Suresh *et al.*, 2016^[23] found that out of 6 isolates, 3 (50%) were strong biofilm producers and Marek *et al.*, 2021^[24] reported that out of 87 isolates of Coagulase Negative *Staphylococcus*, 69 isolates were biofilm producers, out of these, 24 (27.6%) produced weak

biofilms, 11 (25.3%) produced moderate biofilms, and 13 (26.4%) produced strong biofilms. Conclusively, biofilm formation potentially enhances their survivability in any environmental condition. Such biofilm-producing strains are also implicated in chronic infections and are known to intensify disease severity. In the current study, significant numbers of bacterial isolates recovered from poultry litter and feed were resistant against one or more antibiotics regularly prescribed to treat human infections. The multidrug resistance was observed majorly among poultry litter isolates in the present study which may a consequence of irrational or indiscriminate antibiotics usage. These observations imply that poultry farms could act as potential reservoirs for antibiotic-resistant bacteria capable of spreading to humans via the food chain. The occurrence of moderate-level of resistance in poultry isolates is alarming situation possess great economic and major public health concern. The proper initiatives should be taken to control the emergence of such drug resistance pathogens. Although molecular methods could have been used to identify the isolates, financial constraints prevented access to commercial services. However, molecular techniques will be employed in the near future to accurately identify the bacterial species. The studied isolates will also be examined to confirm the presence and expression of virulence genes in both resistant and susceptible strains.

CONCLUSION

This study highlights the presence of multidrug-resistant gram-negative bacteria including *Escherichia spp.*, *Proteus spp.*, and *Pseudomonas spp.* in poultry litter and feed samples, with notable resistance to antibiotics such as ampicillin, cefotaxime, and doxycycline. The detection of virulence factors among these isolates further underscores the potential threat they pose to public

health, particularly through transmission along the food chain. The findings highlight poultry farms as significant reservoirs for antimicrobial-resistant pathogens and underscore the need for prudent antibiotic use in animal agriculture. Implementing surveillance programs, promoting antibiotic stewardship, and exploring synergistic antibiotic combinations are essential strategies to restrict the emergence and dissemination of resistance. These measures are critical for safeguarding both human and animal health in the face of rising antimicrobial resistance.

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